

ORGANIZING EFFECTIVE WAYS OUT OF CLASSROOM ACTIVITIES ACCORDING TO THE SUBJECT.

Amrullayeva Maxliyo Abdurahmonovna

Tashkent Academic Lyceum No.2 of the Ministry of Internal
Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan,

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The purpose of school is to prepare students for life beyond school. Today's society has a higher demand for self-awareness and more specialized skills. One of the easiest ways to help advance students is by incorporating learning experiences out of classroom activities. Taking classroom learning outside can help enrich a student's educational experience by showing them real-life applications of theories that they are learning at school.

Learning out of classroom activities are often authentic, hands-on, interactive and build on classroom learning.

Learning out of classroom activities is the use of places other than the school for teaching and learning. It is about getting children and young people out and about, providing them with challenging, exciting and different experiences to help them learn. Places may refer to a location, activity or workshop, but regardless of where learning outside the classroom takes place, the purpose is the same. Give students a real-world learning experience that will set them up for success in life beyond school.

By the way learning out of classroom activities experiences differ from conventional teaching methods as students may be encouraged to engage a broader range of soft skills such as teamwork, leadership and compromise in their learning environment. Learning out of classroom activities can help teachers create enthusiasm for learning, provide a real-world context and expose students to a range of STEM careers.

Students who experience learning outside the classroom benefit from increased self-esteem and become more engaged in their education. Out of classroom activities are traditionally viewed as an unsupervised activity with a specific learning objective that students can do in their most convenient time. Out-of-classroom activities prepare students for real-life. Challenges, such as time management, independent learning and self-efficacy.

Learning outside the classroom is a broad term that includes: outdoor play, school grounds projects, environmental education, recreational and adventure activities, personal and social development.

Out-of-class activity is a form of organization of personal study of students learning the material in the classroom and extracurricular time. The goal of this type of activity is to promote independence as important personal characteristics and professional skills of a young man, the essence of which lies in the ability to organize, plan, monitor and regulate their activities without assistance and control of the lecturer. The objectives of out of classroom activity may be learning specific knowledge, skills, consolidation and systematization of acquired knowledge, their application to solve practical problems and implementation of creative work.

Traditionally out of class activity is considered as a purposeful, free activity of students in the most convenient time from their point of view. Independent work of students is necessary not only for education, but also for getting professional skills and experience in creative and research activity to solve different problems.

Out of classroom activity depends on its organization and forms.

There are 3 forms of it: individual, teamwork and mass scale.

Individual work includes such tasks as to make a report for 5-10 minutes, a presentation, to write an article etc. All students can take part in this kind of work. It can be carried out constantly or from time to time.

Teamwork might include the preparation for a holiday, different competitions among students who enjoy drawing, singing, reciting poems etc. This work joins the students with the same interests and hobbies.

Mass scale is a form involves carrying out of conferences, Olympiads in foreign languages, exhibitions' organization etc.

In conclusion out of classroom activities gives students the opportunity to work without haste, without fear of negative evaluation from their group-mates or a lecturer, and as well as to choose the optimal pace of work and the conditions of its implementation. In a face-to-face classroom setting, learning happens not only during the class but also after students leave the classroom. Such learning activities are defined as "activities in which students engage during the undergraduate study that are either directly or indirectly related to their learning and performance and occur behind the formal classroom, studio or laboratory setting". Out of classroom activities are traditionally viewed as an unsupervised activity with a specific learning objective that students can do in their most convenient time. Out-of-class activities prepare students for real-life challenges, such as time management, independent learning, and self-efficacy. Such out-of-class activities have many benefits as found in previous researches.

It is also shown that learning well in the classroom does not guaranty that students will also do well outside the classroom.

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